

UDC 021.7:077.5(477)

VASYLYNYNA O. M.

National University «Yuri Kondratyuk Poltava Polytechnic» (Poltava, Ukraine),
e-mail: o.vasylynyna@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0003-0402-4627

DEREVIANKO L. I.

National University «Yuri Kondratyuk Poltava Polytechnic» (Poltava, Ukraine),
e-mail: derevyanko.adye@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0001-6271-6571

DOROSHENKO S. M.

National University «Yuri Kondratyuk Poltava Polytechnic» (Poltava, Ukraine),
e-mail: doroshenko_s_m@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0002-6535-4788**Formation of Image Communications of the Library in the Modern Information Space**

Objective. As part of the study, the analysis of the main components of the library's communication and image policy and the determination of methods for optimizing the activities of libraries in social media are expected.

Methods. To achieve the set objective and solve the specified tasks, a complex use of various research methods was carried out: analysis and synthesis; generalization; systematization; system and component analysis. **Results.** During the research, a theoretical generalization was made and a new solution to the problem of the library image communications formation in the modern information space was proposed, which was embodied in the theoretical justification of the conditions that ensure the effectiveness of new Internet technologies introduction in the work of library institutions. In the process of scientific research, recommendations were made for the popularization of library activities, as well as the modernization of the library image in the Internet environment. The collected and systematized material can be used to create relevant library content in social networks. **Conclusions.** The formation of image communications of the library in the modern information space is a complex and multi-level process associated with the organization of special studies, with the development of the program and plan of the image campaign, and activities system aimed at image elements formation in social media resources. The main direction of libraries development is the systematic implementation of modern information technologies with the aim of popularizing library services for potential readers. Timely adaptation and implementation of information and communication technologies in the activities of libraries will allow them to retain their priority in the future regarding socially significant information realization and preserve themselves as a social institution.

Keywords: image communications of the library; information space; library and information services; Internet technologies; social networks; social media content

Introduction

The rapid development of digital technologies and the global network, which is the Internet, significantly affects the library image, and also provides an opportunity to outline the boundaries of the modern library space. The traditional book collection is already ceasing to be popular because there is a rapid global exclusion of the audience from the book and a gradual fascination with visual and auditory media content.

A serious transformation of the library's image is taking place under the influence of various factors: the global spread of Internet technologies, information space digitalization and gamification, and changes in the need of information consumers, who are taking a direct part in the process of creating content more frequently. So, library workers must actively adapt to changes in the information environment, which means actively learning new approaches to their work.

The basis of a modern library activity should currently be a website, a portal, as well as social media, e-mail, and a virtual environment based on immersive technologies. Such tools should ensure the development of library communications and opinion formation in the most

active part of the target audience. Therefore, nowadays the main task of the library is to effectively organize reading activities in the online mode and fill the Internet environment with socially valuable and relevant content that will help users navigate the information flow and establish interaction with them in the real library space.

Consequently, such a total transformation of the library space creates the need for a radical renewal of libraries' image in accordance with modern trends. Its significant change in the information space is a necessary and relevant process, during which considerable attention should be paid to the search for new approaches that enable the combination of traditional and virtual methods of communication. Active involvement of virtual users, the creation of an attractive and investment IT environment, and the popularization of librarianship among young professionals ensure the creation of a favorable image of the library.

All these factors actualize research in the field of image communications of the modern library. However, currently, there is a lack of scientific works that would reveal the basics of building a virtual library environment; the issues of building the libraries' image communications by maintaining pages in social networks that are popular among young people remain insufficiently covered.

Methods

The theoretical and methodological foundations of research are an organic set of basic approaches, principles, and methods of research on which modern science is based. Among the scientific approaches, synthetic and systemic were used. The main principles of research are objectivity, comprehensiveness, determinism, and continuity.

In order to achieve the set goal and solve the specified tasks, complex use of various methods was carried out: analysis and synthesis (to study the image components, and establish the connection between them in order to obtain a holistic view of the image communications of libraries); generalization (to formulate conclusions, substantiate practical recommendations regarding the possibilities of radical libraries image updating in accordance with modern trends); systematization (to determine the results of using social networks in order to build the library image in the virtual space); system-component analysis (to determine the main components of the library's image in social networks).

The source knowledge base of the research consists of scientific articles and separate educational and methodological works, which are devoted to aspects of the theory and practice of creating the library's image with the help of social media, theoretical and methodological foundations of the library's style formation, construction of the library's image in social networks, as well as development of its multi-vector activity.

Chronological framework of the researched publications – 2012-2022.

Analysis of recent research. The issue of the representation of library institutions in the network space has been reflected in numerous scientific studies. Thus, in the publications by O. Mar'ina (2013), the issue of social and communication technologies was considered, and the feasibility of their introduction as a means of managing the library and information sphere was substantiated. The researcher T. Hbranchak (2016) presented the results of the various social network use analysis by world and Ukraine national libraries in the process of improving library services, revealing the features of individual networks as platforms for the presentation of library products and services. A. Vitushko (2013) analyzed possible ways to solve the problem of safe social network use in the work of library institutions, and M. Samsonov (2012) characterized the peculiarities of libraries' adaptation to the conditions of distribution and use of original content, in particular in the YouTube social network.

Joseph M. Yap (2020) explores what social media supports academic libraries in Kazakhstan during the global pandemic and how they can improve their social media engagement to stay in touch with their users.

The target audience can be informed about the library, its support of users, or other events taking place in the library space, including with the help of social media, A. Miamlina (2020) believes.

R. Palumbo (2022) is looking for the specifics of running virtual reading groups, online laboratories, and social networks that improve the image of a modern library and actively attract users to it during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Despite the fact that the representation of libraries in social networks is being researched quite actively, this phenomenon is so dynamic and multifaceted that some problems deserving detailed coverage remain outside the attention of scientists. Such issues should include the impact of mass media technologies on the formation of the library's image in the information environment, the analysis of the library's presence in the interactive space of social networks, and the search for advertising strategies to build image communications of libraries in the electronic space.

That is exactly why, the purpose of the study is to analyze the main components of the image of a modern library institution, to review new forms of library service related to the use of social media; to define the main types and formats of library content in social media; description of the basic principles of management of official representative offices of book collections in a virtual environment; identifying the main directions and ways of improving image communications of libraries with the help of modern media services.

Results and discussion

The creation of a positive image, as well as the formation of a reliable reputation among the general public, becomes the basis of a modern library institution and the priority direction of its activity. By the image of a modern library, we mean its visible image, which responds to the smallest changes occurring externally – in the social and cultural life of society, and internally – in the library itself. A positive image is formed by the quality of services and the level of library users' service and advertising activities.

The main components for the library's image forming are:

- professional ethics of librarians;
- the website of the library and its representation in popular social networks;
- public relations and advertising of the institution's services;
- design of the library premises.

Creating the image of a modern library institution is a process of two-way interaction, in which the subject of the image which is the image of the library, and the object that perceives this image which is the public, play an active role. The effectiveness of the library's image policy depends on the activities of the team, and the library's management, which together systematically shape the image based on available resources and communication channels.

The concept of "image communications" is understood as a developing system of social interaction, where the image characteristics of libraries are interconnected, which dynamically changes under the influence of various factors.

Image communication is communication during which a set of cognitive, motivational, and expressive components is created and broadcast, ensuring the purposeful formation of a complete image. So, it is all about a special system of social interaction, in which a cognitive and emotional attitude toward the object is purposefully or spontaneously formed on the basis of the

communicative process. The main goal of image communication in library activities is to achieve an accurate understanding of the image created by users of library services.

The modern library as a source of knowledge is currently in the conditions of fierce competition with the Internet, however, the thing that reduces the number of real library visitors can be useful for increasing the "virtual" ones. Multidirectional trends have been observed in society: a certain part loses interest in science due to the deceptive simplicity of obtaining information on the Internet, and the other part is open to any way of obtaining new impressions, skills, and experience.

All this encourages libraries to independently search for ways to spread and popularize scientific knowledge, to create their own niche among various digital sources of information for the user and is implemented through the introduction of new forms of library service related to the use of social networks, blogs, forums, and virtual communities.

Recently, libraries have started to promote their presence on social media. This is a fairly unobtrusive way to attract the attention of readers and encourage them to participate in the life of the library, receive news, and interact with it on social media, and also a successful way to combine the physical space of the library with the digital one – an online page or group. Social media, which are used to promote libraries, have acquired the status of not only a virtual space for acquaintances, communication, etc., but also a convenient means of information exchange, and sometimes they also perform the functions of mass media.

A notable feature of building image communications of libraries in social media is that they are often carried out not for the purpose of attracting a certain number of users, but for the sake of popularizing the site, library, and services, initiating discussion, and spontaneous dissemination of information. For successful promotion in social networks, an important point is that, in addition to the organization's content, it is necessary to create original content specifically for your news feed.

Among the positive functional characteristics that increase the popularity of media services, the following are mentioned: accessibility, openness, practical orientation; mass audience and multi-level interaction; efficiency and interactivity; convenience and variety of forms of communication and tools for a content generation; mobility and integration with other resources (Pavlenko, 2017).

For modern libraries, social media is the main advertising platform, therefore the dissemination of library events and library activities in general with the help of social media is becoming very relevant. Media activity helps to study the target audience, and demand for library services, get feedback, increase attendance at events, and increase activity on the official website. Such communication takes various social forms: users can express their opinion, share experiences and knowledge in comments, establish contacts, and also share news, information, videos, photos, music, recommendations, and other content.

Social media in general include:

1. Social networks. The social network is a combination of electronic technologies as a means of communication and, accordingly, connections between individuals and communities united by related interests, and a promising means for building effective image communications of the library and popularizing library activities, library services, and library institutions.

Key factors of using social networks for libraries are:

- types of applications where the user can create their own record;
- notification technologies related to news distribution;
- a culture of openness that makes content available for distribution and reuse;
- a culture of trust that supports the distribution of content, discussion, and comments;
- social collaboration services that help share images, stories, and comments.

LIBRARY SERVICES FOR SCIENCE AND EDUCATION SUPPORT

Social network tools help convey information to users in a very convenient way, as well as create the image of the library in the virtual space. The presentation of the library on social networks provides an opportunity to quickly inform a large audience about the new editions' arrival, and planned events and to spread this information further.

2. Blog. Nowadays, the library blogosphere reflects both the current problems of the libraries functioning in modern society, and opinions about the problems of the library community.

A blog is also a new marketing tool that allows you to find a new potential user. Many libraries successfully advertise their resources and services, so it is not surprising that librarians begin to fill the virtual world with their blogs, because a blog is a real opportunity to build image communications of libraries and their services.

3. Forums. A forum is a place of "virtual meeting" of leaders and leading specialists of libraries, scientists, teachers of higher education institutions, publishers, authors, readers, information service providers, members and partners of the Ukrainian Library Association in a remote format. Each forum is devoted to current problems of library affairs.

3. Wiki-technologies. Libraries can use wiki technologies in their activities for joint projects, collective work, creation of directories, knowledge bases, documentation development, etc.

Libraries use social media to announce important events, library promotions, and events. Working in social media allows libraries to conduct "branding" activities with maximum effect. As a result of the implementation of creative ideas, there is an interest in network users, and a desire to share information with each other.

Libraries, having realized the advantages of integration into social media, which make it possible to build an optimal selection of services necessary to meet the information needs of an individual on one platform, are gradually expanding their interaction with these services. At the same time, the library receives an additional channel for the implementation of its strategies, the popularization of its own services, especially remote ones, a tool for the dissemination of information on library science, development of library and information technologies (Tereshchenko, 2016).

Libraries need to pay attention to branding and the choice of content formats. Among the trends this year, marketers note a decline in video and instant articles, and a peak in the popularity of messengers, real-time posts, and instant updates. It makes sense for libraries to implement some important functions and trends of social marketing in order to promote their own content more successfully.

Content is the entire informational resource: texts, images, and videos. It plays a significant role in the functioning of the page because it directly affects conversion, ranking in search systems, and audience attraction.

In our opinion, the main criteria for evaluating the quality of a page's content in social media are:

1. Relevance. It is necessary to constantly update information, which is carried out by replacing outdated information with a modern one.

2. Usefulness. The text, as well as the graphic content, must fully correspond to the users' requests.

3. Compliance with legislation. The information posted on social networks must fully comply with the current legislation of Ukraine.

4. Credibility. The materials must not contain "fakes" or deliberate distortions.

5. Variety and good presentation. Optimal combination of different types of content: a combination of text with video, photo, or graphic materials.

6. Literacy. Pages in social networks are filled in accordance with the lexical, stylistic, and orthographic norms of the Ukrainian literary language.

The main types of content in social media are:

1) informative: how-to articles; reviews; answers to frequently asked questions; master classes; check lists; experiments; useful resources, etc.;

2) entertaining content: comics, quotes, riddles and puzzles, anecdotes, photo memes, interesting facts, provocative articles;

3) viral: memes, videos, tests, selected articles, e-books;

4) news;

5) reputable;

6) interactive: articles on hot topics; opinion articles; interactive content test, quizzes, surveys, online calculators, animated infographics; publications about current events.

Content formats in social media are:

1. Text. It is the main one for many resources. These are articles, notes, news, descriptions, press releases, reviews, etc.

Among social networks, which mostly present the textual context of the library, the social network "Facebook" has gained the most popularity.

The library page on Facebook is a channel from which Internet users can get information that interests them. There it is possible to comment, evaluate, receive information, focus your attention on marketing activities, in particular on highlighting the socio-cultural work of the library, library news, and announcements of events.

An important supporting tool for the distribution of textual content is "cloud technology". One of the best options for such technologies is Google Drive. The community administrator has a mailbox on the gmail.com domain, which allows the use of cloud resources. By creating a folder for each event, adding documents there, and providing public access to it, the administrator provides an opportunity for everyone interested to familiarize themselves with the materials (Barannik, 2017).

2. Graphic. Such content is often a supplement to the text, sometimes the main one. Images must meet the following criteria: to have a high resolution; to be unique or such that does not violate the terms of public distribution; to be optimized for the page on the network; to match the design of the page.

Images facilitate the process of perceiving textual content, and also significantly influence users' behavior, and can be an additional source of traffic if they rank well in search systems.

Flickr and Instagram services are the most popular ones among social networks for graphic content.

Flickr.com is a website for posting, viewing, discussing, evaluating, and archiving photo and video materials. It is popular due to the convenient and simple system of uploading and searching for photos, which also enables communication and the creation of thematic groups and social networks. Consequently, it provides opportunities for the library to profitably present its funds, replenish the information base and provide the user with convenient access to documents (Tereshchenko, 2016).

Instagram is a social network based on photo-sharing that allows users to take photos, apply filters to them, and share them through its service and a number of other social networks. Users can upload photos and short videos, follow other users' feeds, and geotag images with place names.

Based on the peculiarities of Instagram, the use of the network by libraries can be effective in the case of prompt posting of information about those events that have just taken place in the institution, or those that will take place soon, for the purpose of their visual advertising, popularization of the library's activities, promotion of its services and products.

3. Video. Video content can be main or additional. It allows you to significantly increase the time the user stays on the page, which has a positive effect on popularity.

With the help of videos, it is possible to diversify the content, demonstrate the services and activities of the library as clearly as possible. The complexity of the forgery and the pervasive impact make such content an effective marketing tool.

The YouTube video service is widely used in the library environment, which is a popular video hosting platform that provides video hosting services. Users can add, view, and comment on certain videos. Due to its simplicity and ease of use, YouTube has become one of the most popular places to host videos. The service contains both professional and amateur videos, including video blogs.

Libraries actively use such video hosting. For example, they create a channel on YouTube and post video materials there, primarily educational videos on working with the electronic catalog, electronic information resources, recordings of television programs and interviews with library professionals, etc. The YouTube video service allows you to view, download and share videos. The site features music videos, films and cartoons, commercials, book trailers, and amateur videos submitted by people from around the world.

4. Audio. Audio information (music, podcasts, interviews, audiobooks) is appropriate on resources of different orientations. In commercial projects, audio feedback from customers is most often used.

Libraries can issue digital audiobooks through OneClickdigital app by Recorded Books publishing, which allows users to download audiobooks to their devices for listening for a certain period of time. This service is an important addition to the services of libraries that strive to include as many digital options as possible for their users.

So, in our time – the time of an incredible amount of data in the information space, it is sometimes difficult for potentially interested visitors to find what they need, therefore, a high-quality representation of library activities using social media becomes especially relevant (Barannik, 2017; Yap, 2020). Such social media can and should be used for the implementation of library tasks and effective communication in both virtual and real environments.

Interesting announcements, aesthetically attractive graphic design, timely updating of information – all these things play a big role in forming a positive image of the library. Multimedia technologies are a field that develops constantly and rapidly, and more and more opportunities arise for the diversification of library activities. Social media dominates among other information resources, such as television and paper media (newspapers and magazines), especially among young people, so the representation of library activities in this way is a very relevant issue precisely in terms of image communications.

Conclusions

During the study, new approaches to the formation of the library's image were analyzed thanks to the activation of social network involvement in order to create an updated image. Some vectors of the developmental effect of social media in the context of library professionals' image communication were also considered.

Therefore, at the present stage, representation in the virtual space of library institutions as modern information centers, which is one of the basic elements of an information society formation, is of particular importance. Representation of libraries in the virtual space is carried out through specialized Internet sites, which are a characteristic feature of the transformation of the existing library service system; their functioning creates conditions for the compliance of library activities with new social needs.

The creation of a modern, promising library's image will be facilitated by the institution's development of an image strategy and a systematic approach to the formation and presentation in an interactive space of the library's image as an institution, the librarian as a specialist, the fund as an object of library activity.

So, the library can position its image:

- 1) as a place for creative work and study;
- 2) as a personal brand of an employee, if the individual is considered as a carrier of knowledge, professional skills, and talent;
- 3) through services to improve information literacy, conducting activities related to the provision of information products and services provided as a result of the library's information research;
- 4) through the collection of the library fund;
- 5) using the website, pages in social networks, and media content produced by the library.

Today, libraries are actively studying the prospects of using social media, services, and the main trends in the use of modern technologies. This provides new opportunities for the presentation of library collections, information products, and services and wide access to them.

The need to use social media to build image communications of modern libraries is determined by a number of factors:

- 1) most tools for building an image in the online environment are free;
- 2) social media covers a large number of virtual users;
- 3) social networks are one of the main means of public communication, which influences the formation of public opinion.

During the research, it was established that social media would not be able to become a universal image component capable of independently bringing the library brand to the desired level, but today it is a rather powerful tool that should not be ignored.

REFERENCES

- Barannik, S. (2017, October). Vykorystannia sotsialnykh media ta multymediinykh tekhnolohii dlia reprezentatsii literaturnoho klubu biblioteky VNZ [Use of social media and multimedia technologies for representation of the literary club of the university library]. In *Sotsialni media dlia bibliotek: seredovyshche, resurs, servis. Materialy kruhloho stolu* (pp. 9-15), Scientific Library of Kharkiv National Medical University, Kharkiv, Ukraine. Retrieved from <https://repo.knmu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/19059> (in Ukrainian)
- Hranchak, T. (2016). Vykorystannia natsionalnymy bibliotekamy sotsmerezh dlia predstavlenia biblioteknykh produktiv i posluh [Usage social networks among national libraries for presentation of library products and services]. *Biblioteknyi visnyk*, 1(231), 18-29. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/bv_2016_1_5 (in Ukrainian)
- Mar'ina, O. (2013). Sotsialno-komunikatsiini tekhnolohii yak zasib upralinnia bibliotekno-informatsiinoiu sferoiu diialnosti. *Visnyk knyzhkovoï palaty*, 3, 26-28. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/vkp_2013_3_10 (in Ukrainian)
- Miamlina, A. V. (2020). Marketing communications: reading promotion programs in academic libraries. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 5, 20-24. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2020_220650 (in English)
- Palumbo, R. (2022). Thriving in the post-Covid-19 era: a new normality for libraries' service offering. *Library Management*, 43(8-9), 536-562. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-05-2022-0051> (in English)

- Pavlenko, T. (2017, October). Sotsialni media u profesiinomu rozvytku bibliotechnoho fakhivtsia [Social media in professional development of the library specialist]. In *Sotsialni media dlia bibliotek: seredovyshe, resurs, servis. Materialy kruhloho stolu* (pp. 68-73), Scientific Library of Kharkiv National Medical University. Kharkiv, Ukraine. Retrieved from <https://repo.knmu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/19059> (in Ukrainian)
- Samsonov, M. (2012). Reklama bibliotek v onlainovykh sotsialnykh merezhakh. *Naukovi pratsi Natsionalnoi biblioteky Ukrainy im. V. I. Vernadskoho*, 33, 532-542. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/npnbuimviv_2012_33_49 (in Ukrainian)
- Tereshchenko, I. (2016, October). Vizualnyi bibliotechnyi kontent u sotsialnykh media. In *Biblioteka. Nauka. Komunikatsiia: formuvannia natsionalnoho informatsiinoho prostoru. Materialy mizhnar. nauk. konf.* (pp. 296-298), Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine. Kyiv, Ukraine. Retrieved from <http://www.irbis-nbuv.gov.ua/everlib/item/er-0003707> (in Ukrainian)
- Vitushko, A. (2013). Problema vykorystannia v bibliotechnomu informatsiinomu vyrobnytstvi sotsialnykh merezh z tochky zoru informatsiinoi bezpeky. *Naukovi pratsi Natsionalnoi biblioteky Ukrainy im. V. I. Vernadskoho*, 36, 181-191. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/npnbuimviv_2013_36_19 (in Ukrainian)
- Yap, J. M. (2020). Library promotion and user engagement in pandemic times: the case of Kazakhstan. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 5, 39-46. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2020_220692 (in English)

VASYLYNYNA O. M.

Національний університет «Полтавська політехніка імені Юрія Кондратюка» (Полтава, Україна), e-mail: o.vasylynyna@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0003-0402-4627

DEREVIANKO L. I.

Національний університет «Полтавська політехніка імені Юрія Кондратюка» (Полтава, Україна), e-mail: derevyanko.adye@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0001-6271-6571

DOROSHENKO S. M.

Національний університет «Полтавська політехніка імені Юрія Кондратюка» (Полтава, Україна), e-mail: doroshenko_s_m@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0002-6535-4788

Формування іміджевих комунікацій бібліотеки в сучасному інформаційному просторі

Мета. У рамках дослідження передбачається аналіз основних складників комунікаційно-іміджевої політики бібліотеки та визначення методів оптимізації діяльності бібліотек у соціальних медіа. **Методика.** Для досягнення поставленої мети й розв'язання зазначених завдань здійснено комплексне використання різноманітних дослідницьких методів: аналізу і синтезу; узагальнення; систематизації; системно-компонентного аналізу. **Результати.** Під час дослідження здійснено теоретичне узагальнення й запропоновано нове вирішення проблеми стосовно формування іміджевих комунікацій бібліотеки в сучасному інформаційному просторі, що знайшло втілення в теоретичному обґрунтуванні умов, які забезпечують ефективність впровадження нових інтернет-технологій в роботу бібліотечних установ. У процесі наукового пошуку складено рекомендації щодо популяризації діяльності бібліотек, а також модернізації бібліотечного іміджу в інтернет-середовищі. Зібраний і систематизований матеріал можна застосовувати для створення актуального контенту бібліотеки в соціальних мережах. **Висновки.** Формування іміджевих комунікацій бібліотеки в сучасному інформаційному просторі – це складний та багаторівневий процес, пов'язаний з організацією спеціальних досліджень, з розробкою програми та плану іміджевої кампанії, системи заходів, орієнтованих на формування елементів іміджу в соціальних медіаресурсах. Основним напрямом розвитку бібліотек є системне впровадження сучасних інформаційних технологій з метою популяризації бібліотечних послуг потенційним читачам. Своєчасна адаптація й впровадження

LIBRARY SERVICES FOR SCIENCE AND EDUCATION SUPPORT

інформаційно-комунікаційних технологій у діяльність бібліотек дозволить їм у перспективі зберегти пріоритет щодо реалізації соціально значущої інформації та зберегти себе як соціальний інститут.

Ключові слова: іміджеві комунікації бібліотеки; інформаційний простір; бібліотечно-інформаційні послуги; інтернет-технології; соціальні мережі; контент соціальних медіа

Received: 19.07.2022

Accepted: 24.11.2022